

Determinants Affecting Service Supply Capacity: A Case Study Of Logistics Enterprises In Dong Nai Province

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 25, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: June 03, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Service, Supply, Capacity, Logistics, Enterprises, and LHU.</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5068211</p>	<p><i>In the current international economic integration context and the logistics enterprises of Dong Nai province, there has been a remarkable maturity step in the number of participating businesses and the professionalism in service provision. But this breakthrough is still not sustainable, lacking a complete service delivery process and skills, lack of connectivity and coverage in-service network, weak technical technology, and customer service policies. Therefore, this article determined the factors affecting logistics enterprises' service supply capacity in Dong Nai province. The author conducted a study of the data from 500 customers using logistics enterprises in Dong Nai province. The author used the SEM model for data analysis. Finally, four key factors affecting logistics enterprises' service supply capacity in Dong Nai province with a statistical significance of 1%.</i></p>

Introduction

Currently, logistics enterprises in Dong Nai province face a significant challenge that, according to the commitments of the newly signed Free Trade Agreements, typically the EU-Vietnam Free Trade Agreement (EVFTA). Besides, Vietnam's logistics industry has to expand significantly more than the WTO's expansion by Chiu, F. C. (2017), Ellinger, A. E. and Ketchen, D. J. (2018). This service means that foreign competitors, especially the EU, will directly participate in Vietnam services. Managers lose the intermediary role of domestic logistics enterprises, market share will continue declining, and competition pressure increases by Lu, C. S., and Yang, C. C. (2010).

Without timely change, the more integrated, the more domestic logistics businesses will lag. Sanders, N. R., and Premus, R. (2015) will be increasingly distant from the distance with international logistics enterprises. This service is both a challenge and a driving force for domestic logistics businesses to change their minds and enormously change their minds by Stefansson, G. J. (2016).

To survive and develop sustainably, Vietnamese logistics enterprises in Dong Nai need to change towards modernity, expand the reach for logistics activities. And enhance connectivity to the chain between logistics enterprises to better respond to customer requests by Fulcoins, F; Hiesse, V. and Paché, G. (2011). Therefore, researching the logistics enterprises' service delivery capacity in Dong Nai province is an urgent requirement. Stemming from the above analysis, the author has chosen the content of the research topic: determinants affecting service supply capacity: a case study of logistics enterprises in Dong Nai province. Based on the research result above, the author had some recommendations to enhance logistics enterprises' service supply capacity.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Service supply capacity (SSC)

The logistics enterprise's service delivery capacity can integrate and deploy resources to meet the customer's logistics needs in pursuit of better service performance by Nur, F. M. Z; Abdullah, A. M. AND Sazali A. W. (2017). Besides, logistics enterprises need to effectively maintain and manage the organizational learning characteristics and transform learning outcomes into strategies, tactics, and logistics management operations to support and develop more capacity to provide Sonia C. R. and Tomas, F. G. (2015).

The ability to recognize and respond to customer needs(RCN)

The ability to recognize and respond to customer needs can differentiate products or services to enhance customer differentiation by Töyli, J. and David, H. K. (2018), including customer service and quality logistics services. This capacity is also known as integrating into the customer or focusing on the customer Zhang, D. F. (2016). The ability to serve customers includes flexibility (adapting to unusual and diverse customer requirements) and the ability to respond Walters, D. (2016). Based on the concept mentioned above and studies, the author gives hypothesis H1 following:

Hypothesis H1: The ability to recognize and respond to customer needs (RCN) positively impacts logistics enterprises' service supply capacity in Dong Nai province.

Operational capacity (OPC)

Operational capacity contributes to improved service performance and quality and has a significant positive relationship to the implementation of logistics businesses by Shang, K. C. and Narlow, P. Y. (2017) and Stefansson, G. J. (2016). Operational competence is essentially the ability to provide specific services requested by the customer. These are the basic capabilities of logistics service providers that are often closely linked with the business's tangible assets. Operational capacity concretized through transporting, providing warehouse space, ensuring delivery time, ensuring cargo safety, and flexibly responding to urgent/sudden requests for customers' export by Stank, T. P. (2013). Timely response to requirements, at the right time, at the right place, assisting customers in solving arising problems and providing accurate information that reflects the operational capacity of logistics businesses. Compared to Mitrega, M. (2018) and Tahir, I. M. and Baker, N. M. (2017). Based on the concept mentioned above and studies, the author gives hypothesis H2 following:

Hypothesis H2: The operational capacity (OPC) positively impacts logistics enterprises' service supply capacity in Dong Nai province.

Information management capacity (IMC)

Information management capacity meets the supply chain's operational and strategic information needs to balance supply-demand and facilitate communication with the supply chain by Sanders, N. R., and Premus, R. (2015). This capacity significantly affects three essential aspects of logistics service providers' competitive advantage: cost reduction, innovative service delivery, customization, and service quality improvement by Lai, K. H. and Cheng, T. C. (2018) and Mentzer, J. T. and Michelle, B. (2014). Information is the most potential factor that can help logistics operations become more responsive to customer needs while also helping to reduce costs. The information combined with the logistics system forms the logistics information system by Lu, C. S., and Yang, C. C. (2010). Based on the concept as mentioned earlier and studies, the author gives hypothesis H3 following:

Hypothesis H3: The operational capacity (OPC) positively impacts logistics enterprises' service supply capacity in Dong Nai province.

Integration and connectivity (IAC)

Integration capacity is an enterprise's ability to combine all available resources and competencies, such as recognizing by Gligor, D. M. and Holcomb, M. C. (2012). Enterprises respond to customer needs, operational competence, information management capacity, the ability to connect and harmonize them to improve business results and create a sustainable competitive advantage in rapidly changing business conditions by Chapman, R. L. and Scoosay, C. (2013) and Chapman, R. L. and Scoosay, C. (2013). In the rapidly changing business environment, the integration capacity helps the enterprise adapt to the fluctuations of internal and external factors. Logistics businesses need to flexibly integrate many services to ensure package elements in service delivery, which is the basis to compete with companies from abroad by Brah, S. A. and Lim, H. Y. (2016) and Stank, T. P. (2013). Based on the concept as mentioned above and studies, the author gives hypothesis H4 following:

Hypothesis H4: Integration and connectivity (IAC) positively impact logistics enterprises' service supply capacity in Dong Nai province.

(Source: Researcher proposed)

Figure 1. A research model for factors affecting the service supply capacity of logistics enterprises in Dong Nai province

METHODS OF RESEARCH

The research uses a combined qualitative and quantitative analysis. Qualitative research is carried out to model and supplement, and explain the results from quantitative data. The author' research process for factors affecting the service supply capacity of logistics enterprises in Dong Nai province following:

(Source: Author proposed)

Figure 2. A research process for factors affecting the service supply capacity of logistics enterprises in Dong Nai province

Step 1: Theoretical basis, previous studies -Model: the author had a desk study with secondary data from earlier studies on service supply capacity. In this step, the author studied the theories from classical to modern and selected service supply capacity theory by Hair, J., Anderson, R., Tatham, R., & Black, W. (2010).

Step 2: Qualitative research, in-depth interviews on a narrow scale -testing model: the author interviewed 35 experts in service supply chain management and preliminary testing of the research model.

Step 3: Preliminary quantitative research (N = 100) - questionnaire: This step aims to survey data from 100 customers using logistics services of enterprises in Dong Nai province.

Interviews were conducted in 3/2020-7/2020 with the direct interview method and telephone interview by Hair, J., Anderson, R., Tatham, R., & Black, W. (2010).

Step 4: Formal quantitative research (N = 500) - questionnaire: The pilot survey was conducted by interviewing directly through questionnaires for 50 logistics enterprises with 500 customers but 465 samples processed, lacking 35 customers. The purpose of this is to standardize terminology and correct wording errors and interview methods to get the best survey results before a large model launched by Hair, J., Anderson, R., Tatham, R., & Black, W. (2010).

Step 5: The author analyzed reliability coefficients Cronbach's alpha, explore factors analyzing - EFA, confirming factors – CFA Analysis of the SEM. Besides, quantitative research aims to test the research model's hypotheses on factors affecting the service supply capacity of logistics enterprises in Dong Nai province. The author processed by SPSS 20.0 and Amos software to evaluate the scale's value and reliability; test research models and research hypotheses. Testing is P-value > 5%; CMIN/df ≤ 2.0, some cases CMIN/df maybe ≤ 3.0 or < 5.0; GFI, TLI, CFI ≥ 0.9. However, according to recent researchers' opinions, GFI is still acceptable when it is more significant than 0.8; RMSEA ≤ 0.08. Apart from the above criteria, the test results must also ensure synthetic reliability > 0.6; the Average variance extracted must be greater than 0.5 by Hair, J., Anderson, R., Tatham, R., & Black, W. (2010).

Step 5: Test research models and hypotheses. Finally, the author had conclusions and Policy implications.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Testing Cronbach's alpha for factors affecting the service supply capacity of logistics enterprises in Dong Nai province following:

Table 1. Testing of cronbach's alpha for the factors affecting the service supply capacity

Items		Cronbach's alpha
The ability to recognize and respond to customer needs (RCN)		0.950
RCN1	Ability to provide diverse types of services	0.927
RCN2	Ability to provide services on a wide range	0.942
RCN3	Ability to provide quality service following the price level	0.943
RCN4	Service innovation ability to keep up with customer needs	0.924
Operational capacity (OPC)		0.861
OPC1	Ability to meet the delivery time as committed	0.815
OPC2	Ability to ensure the safety of goods, deliver the right quantity and volume as committed	0.817
OPC3	Flexibility with customer urgent requests	0.848
OPC4	Ability to advise customers on suitable service options	0.812
Information management capacity (IMC)		0.943
IMC1	The ability to collect and process information quickly, accurately, and effectively	0.909
IMC2	Ability to collect highly reliable information	0.936
IMC3	The ability to fully, accurately, and promptly communicate information	0.943
IMC4	High information security	0.914

Table 1. Continued

Integration and connectivity (IAC)		0.945
IAC1	Good ability to connect internal resources	0.921
IAC2	Ability to relate well with customers in the service delivery process	0.942
IAC3	Ability to flexibly integrate many customers on the same route	0.934
IAC4	Ability to flexibly integrate many services to ensure the package element	0.914
Service supply capacity (SSC)		0.863
SSC1	The ability to recognize and respond to customer needs (RCN) positively impacts the service supply capacity of logistics enterprises in Dong Nai province	0.844
SSC2	The operational capacity (OPC) positively impacts the service supply capacity of logistics enterprises in Dong Nai province	0.789
SSC3	Information management capacity (IMC) positively impacts the service supply capacity of logistics enterprises in Dong Nai province	0.858
SSC4	Integration and connectivity (IAC) positively impact the service supply capacity of logistics enterprises in Dong Nai province	0.800

(Source: Researcher proposed by SPSS 20.0)

Table 1 shows that five components: (1) The ability to recognize and respond to customer needs (RCN), (2) Operational capacity (OPC), (3) Information management capacity (IMC), (4) Integration and connectivity (IAC) and (5) Service supply capacity (SSC). Five components of Cronbach's alpha are high 0.6.

The ability to recognize and respond to customer needs (RCN) of Cronbach's alpha is 0.950. The operational capacity (OPC) of Cronbach's alpha is 0.861. Besides, the information management capacity (IMC) of Cronbach's alpha is 0.943. Moreover, the integration and connectivity (IAC) of Cronbach's alpha is 0.945. The service supply capacity (SSC) of Cronbach's alpha is 0.863. This result is very consistent with the actual survey data in Dong Nai province.

(Source: Data processed by SPSS 20.0 and Amos)

Figure 3. Testing CFA for factors affecting the service supply capacity of logistics enterprises in Dong Nai province

Table 2. Testing coefficients for factors affecting the service supply capacity of logistics enterprises in Dong Nai province

Relationships			Unstandardized Estimate	Standardized Estimate	SE.	CR.	P	Hypothesis
SSC	<---	RCN	0.084	0.127	0.030	2.829	0.005	Accepted
SSC	<---	OPC	0.127	0.182	0.035	3.605	***	Accepted
SSC	<---	IMC	0.098	0.159	0.027	3.626	***	Accepted
SSC	<---	IAC	0.273	0.397	0.031	8.884	***	Accepted

(Source: Data processed by SPSS 20.0, Amos)

Table 2 showed four factors affecting logistics enterprises' service supply capacity in Dong Nai province with a significance level of 0.01.

(Source: Data processed by SPSS 20.0, Amos)

Figure 4. Testing sem for factors affecting the service supply capacity of logistics enterprises in Dong Nai province

Table 3. Testing coefficients of bootstrap (n = 35.000) for factors affecting the service supply capacity of logistics enterprises in Dong Nai province

Parameter			SE	SE-SE	Mean	Bias	SE-Bias
SSC	<---	RCN	0.032	0.000	0.083	-0.001	0.001
SSC	<---	OPC	0.037	0.000	0.125	-0.002	0.001
SSC	<---	IMC	0.030	0.000	0.099	0.000	0.000
SSC	<---	IAC	0.032	0.000	0.271	-0.003	0.001

(Source: Data processed by SPSS 20.0, Amos)

Table 3 showed that the bootstrap test results are very good with a sample of 35.000 customers. These results indicated that four factors affect the service supply capacity of logistics enterprises in Dong Nai province with a significance level of 0.01. Based on the above output, the author had conclusions and policy implications follow.

Conclusions

In particular, both Vietnamese and logistics enterprises face challenges due to the rapid and unpredictable business environment changes. And increasingly fierce competition pressure in the domestic and foreign market. With the research objectives set out, the research has focused on clarifying the following theoretical and practical issues.

(1) The study had contributed to the theory about systematizing in logistics. Besides, the article continued supplementing and developing approaches that studied logistics enterprises' service delivery capacity. This result clarifies the ability to provide logistics enterprises and forms a theoretical framework related to the business's service delivery capacity.

(2) The author inherits foreign research; research has clarified factors constituting the service delivery capacity of logistics enterprises. They are proposing a model to evaluate the service delivery capacity of logistics enterprises in Dong Nai province. This factor considered one of the most successful researches, contributing to consolidating and completing the theoretical basis of logistics enterprises' service delivery capacity.

(3) The study identifies environmental factors affecting the service delivery capacity of logistics enterprises in Dong Nai province.

(4) Based on testing the factors affecting logistics enterprises' service delivery capacity, the author suggests that governance contributes to improving service delivery capacity. The author had policy implications below.

Policy implications

The logistics enterprise in Dong Nai province should take the following recommendations:

(1) Logistics enterprises need to pay attention to the investment of tangible and intangible resources; this is the fundamental factor to create each business's capacity. For large companies with a network of assets they own, it is necessary to have connections with external resources to meet customers' needs best. Small and medium enterprises with less physical resources should focus more on human resources and information. In particular, they clearly define the importance of critical resources, having a strategy to integrate and deploy resources to form the business's core competencies. Focusing on developing core competencies is an essential factor for companies to gain a competitive advantage and maintain sustainable development.

(2) Customer service policies are built not only for customers to grasp and understand the business's service policy but also to help logistics businesses protect themselves against risks and unexpected circumstances. Unexpected force majeure occurred. Through a widely publicized customer service policy, customers will obtain necessary information about the types of services to be provided and let customers know what to do when the service is not available. Responding firms, for example, excess weight of the consignment, cargo insurance conditions. Customer service policy is established based on time standards, flexibility, service stability, and cost. They are installing a department to take charge of the tasks related to contacting customers, consulting, and answering questions from customers, thereby increasing a good relationship and depicting a professional image. Business need in the eyes of customers. Among other things, resolving complaints is the customer service department's most important task. This result is an opportunity for businesses to re-establish relationships with customers, help enterprises to assess the quality of services provided accurately, the ability to meet customers' needs, and take corrective measures.

(3) Logistics businesses will sign agreements with partners to deploy support services to customers in the package direction. Accordingly, the bank will perform professional operations such as guiding customers to open letters of credit, procedures, and payment methods. Insurance companies will provide insurance packages for merchandise related to the customer's open letter of credit. Logistics enterprises will undertake the remaining stages related to logistics operations. Logistics businesses link with banks to produce products related to the payment of customer service charges. Thereby, managers will make the payment of service charges through banks selected by the logistics enterprise. The benefit of such service fee payment will shorten the transaction time with a simple payment process, maximizing customers' conditions to deliver goods continuously.

(4) Facing the trend of the 4th industrial revolution, logistics businesses must set up an independent department to collect and analyze customer needs. The results obtained are vital information to help enterprises build and design product packages to meet customer requirements. If done well and correctly, market research will effectively create different services for your business compared to other companies. Besides, only focusing on developing and exploiting traditional services will gradually cause Vietnamese logistics enterprises to lose customers to competitors from abroad gradually. Expand and diversify logistics services to meet the actual requirements of providing package solutions. Value-added services that logistics businesses need to pay attention to, research and deploy are goods quality inspection, return recall, demand forecasting, insurance brokerage, order management, management of information systems.

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